

Photodegradation of Safranin-O dye using visible irradiation and aqueous suspension of ZnO in a slurry batch reactor

Brijesh Pare^{a*}, S. B. Jonnalagadda^b, Hitendra S. Tomar^c, Pardeep Singh^a and V. W. Bhagwat^c

^aLaboratory of Photocatalysis, Govt. Madhav Science College, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : brijeshpare2009@gmail.com, pardeepchem@gmail.com

^bSchool of Chemistry, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa

^cSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Abstract : A detailed investigation of photocatalytic degradation of Safranin-O dye has been carried out in the presence of aqueous suspension of ZnO irradiated with visible light in a batch reactor. It was observed that photocatalytic degradation of Safranin-O obeys pseudo-first order reaction according to Langmuir-Hinselwood model. The effects of various probable influencing factors viz. irradiation time, initial dye concentration, catalyst loading, light intensity, presence of H₂O₂, K₂S₂O₈, Na₂CO₃ and NaCl on the degradation efficiency were systematically studied. The decolourization and extent of degradation of the dye were determined by UV-Visible spectrophotometer and COD reflux method respectively. COD value approximately dropped to zero with the degrading efficiency being about 100% after 3 h. The complete mineralization was confirmed by COD analysis and probable mechanism for the degradation of Safranin-O is proposed.

Keywords : Safranin-O, photocatalysis degradation, zinc oxide, mineralization.

Introduction

From the ecological and physiological point of view, the effluents including dyes from industries are the most expressive pollutants¹. The elimination of toxic chemicals from waste water is currently one of the most important subjects in pollution control. Organics which may be found as pollutants in wastewater effluents from industrial or domestic sources must be removed or destroyed before discharge to environment. Recently, it has been demonstrated that semiconducting materials mediating photocatalytic degradation of organics can be the alternatives to the conventional methods for the removal of organic pollutant from water²⁻⁶. It is a well established fact that the illumination of these particles with light energy greater than the band gap energy of the semiconductor ($h\nu > E_g$) produces excited high energy states of electron and that migrates to the surface of the particle and initiate a wide range of chemical redox reaction, which can lead to complete mineralization of organic pollutants. One of the major advantages of the heterogeneous photocatalytic oxidation process over existing technologies is that no

further requirement for secondary disposal process. The photocatalytic process can mineralize the hazardous chemicals to carbon dioxide, water and simple mineral acids⁷. Photocatalysts can be reused or recycled for photocatalytic treatment. Due to their high photosensitivity, non-toxic nature, and large band gap TiO₂ and ZnO are most preferable materials for the photocatalytic oxidation. Out of these two TiO₂ is an UV-light activated photocatalyst. Recent studies focus on the photocatalytic oxidation of organic pollutants mediated by TiO₂ particles in aqueous dispersions under UV-light irradiation. However, solar UV-light reaching the surface of the earth and available to excite TiO₂ is relatively small (approximately 4% of the AMI solar spectrum) and artificial UV-light source are somewhat expensive. Therefore, present work has been focused on exploring means to utilize effectively the visible light⁸⁻¹⁰ sources for treating polluted wastewater containing dye under investigation by using ZnO in the form of slurry.

Present study provides results describing the photodegradation of Safranin-O dye in aqueous ZnO slurry

monitored by chemical oxygen demand (COD) measurements and UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Safranin-O (SO) (3,7-diamino-2,8-dimethyl-5-phenyl phenazinium chloride) is a water soluble dye, which exhibits a sharp absorption peak in the visible region ($\lambda_{\max} = 520 \text{ nm}$) and with no shift due to variation in acidic pH. It is a phenazinium class dyes extensively used as mordants to cotton, silk and wool because of its stability, brilliant colors and fastness to light. The basic structure of Safranin-O is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structure of Safranin-O.

Experimental

Safranin-O dye (Aldrich) and was used as received. All chemicals used were of AR grade. The photocatalyst, ZnO used in the study was obtained from Merck, about 99% pure. All the solutions were prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of compound in double distilled water. The irradiation experiments were carried out in a batch reactor with dimension of $7.5 \times 6 \text{ cm}$ (height \times diameter) provided with a water circulation arrangement in order to maintain the temperature in the range of $25\text{--}30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The irradiation was carried out using 500 W halogen lamp. During the photocatalytic experiment, the slurry composed of dye solution and catalyst was placed in the reactor and stirred magnetically for agitation with simultaneous exposure to visible light. At specific time intervals samples were withdrawn and to remove the ZnO particles the solution samples were centrifuged to assess the extent of decolourisation and degradation photometrically. The intensity of light was measured by a digital lux-meter (Lutron LX -101). The pH was constantly monitored and not adjusted unless otherwise stated. The detection was realized at 520 nm. The chemical oxygen demand (COD) was measured by the closed reflux method employing potassium dichromate as the oxidant under acidic condition. The unreacted oxidant was determined by titrating with ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferrion indicator¹¹.

The photodegradation efficiency for each sample was calculated from the following expression :

$$\eta = \frac{\text{COD}_0 - \text{COD}_t}{\text{COD}_0} \times 100$$

where, η = photodegradation efficiency, COD_0 = COD of dye solution before irradiation and COD_t = COD of dye solution after irradiation for time t .

Results and discussion

Photodecomposition kinetics of Safranin-O (SO) :

The profiles of the photocatalytic degradation of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ dye solution containing 200 mg ZnO as function of irradiation time under varied conditions is illustrated in Fig. 1. A perusal of the Fig. 2 shows, a negligible decrease in the concentration of dye by irradiation in the absence of ZnO or in the presence of ZnO without

Fig. 2. Photodecomposition of Safranin-O as function of irradiation. $[\text{SO}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{ZnO}] = 200 \text{ mg/50 mL}$ and light intensity = 17500 lux and pH = 6.2.

light source. It is evident from the figure that the photolysis of the Safranin-O solution in the presence of the ZnO leads to the disappearance of the compound. The blank experiments with either illuminating SO^+ or with the suspension containing ZnO and SO in the dark, showed that both illumination and the catalyst were necessary for the destruction of dye. As per literature reports, the photocatalytic degradation of the solute/dye follows pseudo-first order kinetics. It is rationalized in terms of the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model, which is modified to accommodate reactions occurring at a solid-liquid interface, as^{5,12,13} :

$$r_0 = \frac{k_r K C_0}{(1 + K C_0)} \quad (1)$$

where r_0 is the rate of disappearance of the dye and C_0 its initial concentration. K represents the equilibrium adsorption constant of the dye on ZnO particles and k_r represents the limiting rate of the reaction at maximum coverage under the experimental conditions. The integrated form is

$$t = 1/Kk_r \ln (C_0/C) + (C_0 - C)/k_r \quad (2)$$

where t is the time required for the initial concentration of dye C_0 to become C . At low concentration of the dye, the second term in eq. (2) is negligible compared to the first. On neglecting the second term, the final form of the equation reduces to

$$\ln (C_0/C) = k_r K t = k t \quad (3)$$

where k is the apparent rate constant of the photocatalytic degradation.

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k} \quad (4)$$

With the initial concentration of dye 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ dye solution containing 200 mg of ZnO and light intensity 17500 lux, the rate constant found to be 0.040 min⁻¹ and the decolourisation half life is 17.32 min, while for the dye to be degraded half of its original concentration, determined through COD determination, is around 90 min as shown in the Table 1. Complete degradation of the dye takes 3 h.

Table 1. Effect of irradiation period

Initial concentration of dye = 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³,
amount of ZnO = 200 mg/50 mL, pH = 6.12,
light intensity = 17500 lux and
Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

Irradiation period (min)	COD (mg/L)	Photodegradation efficiency
0	64	0
30	52	18.7
60	44	31.2
90	34	46.8
120	20	68.7
150	8	87.5
180	0	100.0

Effect of dye concentration :

The dependence of the initial reaction rate on the ini-

tial concentration of SO⁺ is depicted in the Table 2. It is obvious that the rate increases with the increase of the initial concentration of SO until it reaches maximum value

Table 2. Effect of dye concentration

[ZnO] = 200 mg, light intensity = 17500 lux, pH = 6.12 and
Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

Initial dye concentration (10 ⁻⁵ mol dm ⁻³)	k (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
1.0	0.013	53.30
1.5	0.016	43.30
2.0	0.040	17.32
2.5	0.020	34.65
3.0	0.018	38.50
3.5	0.014	49.50
4.0	0.011	63.00

and thereafter it goes on decreasing. The decrease in reaction rate values with increase in initial concentration of the dye can be ascribed to the following reasons : (1) Decrease in the path length of the photons entering the solution due to impermeability of the solution. (2) The increase in concentration of the dye demands an increase catalyst surface, but the irradiation time and the amount of catalyst has been kept constant. Hence, the relative number of O₂^{*} and OH^{*} attacking the dye molecules decrease. Thus, the degradation rate decreases considerably with increase in concentration of the dye.

Effect of ZnO loading :

The effect of change in the amount of photocatalyst on the disappearance of the dye has been investigated employing different concentrations of ZnO varying from 100–600 mg/50 mL of dye solution (Table 3). It is obvious that the rate increases with an increase amount of catalyst up to a level corresponding to the optimum of

Table 3. Effect of ZnO loading

[SO⁺] = 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, light intensity = 17500 lux,
pH = 6.12 and Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

ZnO (mg)	k (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
100	0.030	23.10
200	0.040	17.32
300	0.045	15.40
400	0.051	13.58
500	0.049	14.14
600	0.043	16.11

light absorption. For the dye concentration of 2.0×10^{-5} M, the change in the ZnO amount from 100–400 mg/50 mL has increased the apparent rate constant from 0.030 to 0.051 min^{-1} and decreased the $t_{1/2}$ value from 23.10 to 13.58 min. Further increase in the amount of ZnO to 600 mg/50 mL, has decreased the k value. These observations can be rationalised in terms of availability of active sites on ZnO surface and the penetration of photoactivating light into the suspension. Owing to an increase in the number of ZnO particles as the concentration of catalyst increased, the availability of active sites increase, but the light penetration and the photoactivated volume of the suspension shrink. Further, the scattering of light also increases with increase in catalyst loading^{14–18}. The trade off between these two effects is that at low solute concentration, when there are excess active sites, the balance between the opposing effects is evenly poised and change in the amount of ZnO makes little difference to the reaction rate. At high solute concentration availability of excess active sites outweighs the diminishing photoactivated volume and substantially high k value is obtained at increase in ZnO concentration¹². The increased amount of ZnO increase the quantity of photons absorbed as well. Further increase in catalyst concentration beyond 400 mg/50 mL may result in deactivation of activated molecules due to collision with ground state molecules as shown below¹⁹.

ZnO^* : ZnO with active species adsorbed on its surface.

$\text{ZnO}^\#$: deactivated form of ZnO^* shielding by ZnO may also take place.

Furthermore, the decrease in rate constant at high catalyst concentration are due to other phenomena that may take place like agglomeration (particle-particle interaction) which result in a loss of surface area available for light harvesting.

Effect of H_2O_2 :

The addition of an oxidant into a semiconductor suspension has been proved to enhance the rate of degradation of the organic pollutant^{4,5,21–26}. The photocatalytic degradation of Safranin-O has been severely affected by the addition of hydrogen peroxide (Table 4). On adding H_2O_2 in the concentration range from 2.0×10^{-4} to 6.0

Table 4. Effect of hydrogen peroxide

H_2O_2 (mol dm ⁻³)	k (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
0.0	0.040	17.28
2.0×10^{-4}	0.048	14.43
4.0×10^{-4}	0.054	12.83
6.0×10^{-4}	0.064	10.82
8.0×10^{-4}	0.050	13.83
1.0×10^{-4}	0.032	21.65

$\times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, rate constant values first increases but after reaching a maxima a fall in the rate constant values has been found. The initial increase in the reaction rate on addition of H_2O_2 can be attributed to the formation of OH^\bullet radicals responsible for the photocatalytic oxidation and it inhibits the electron-hole recombination as well. The oxidizing power of hydrogen radical is 2.05 times more than chlorine, 1.58 times more than H_2O_2 and 1.35 times more than ozone. H_2O_2 increases the rate of hydroxyl radical formation through three ways : Firstly, it could act as an alternative electron acceptor to oxygen (eq. (7)), which might restrain the bulk composite of the photo-excited electrons and holes. This should consequently increase the rate of photocatalytic process. Secondly, the reduction of H_2O_2 at the conductance band would also produce hydroxyl radicals. Even if H_2O_2 was not reduced at the conductance band it could accept an electron from superoxide again producing hydroxyl radicals (eq. (7)). Thirdly, the self-decomposition by illumination would also produce hydroxyl radicals (eq. (8)) :

At high concentration, the hydrogen peroxide adsorbed on the photocatalytic surface could effectively scavenge not only the photocatalytic surface formed $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals (eqs. (10) and (11)), but also the photo-generated holes (h^+_{VB}) (eq. (12)) and thus inhibit the major pathway for heterogeneous generation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals^{27,28} :

It is worth mentioning here that HO_2^* radicals are less reactive than OH^* , therefore, have negligible contribution in the dye degradation.

Effect of irradiation time :

Fig. 2 presents the % degradation of the dye at different irradiation period at optimum catalyst loading and dye concentration. Under the experimental condition complete degradation of the dye has completed in 180 min of irradiation. The photocatalytic degradation of the dye takes place on the hydroxylated surface of semiconductor ZnO, where *OH and O_2^{*-} radicals are trapped in the holes of reactive species. The *OH radicals are responsible for the breakdown of dye molecules adsorbed on the surface of ZnO due to increase in *OH and O_2^{*-} radicals increase with increase in irradiation period²⁹.

Effect of pH :

The pH is an important parameter for photocatalytic processes. The properties of solid-electrolyte interference i.e. the electrical double layer, can get modified as the pH of the medium changes. Consequently, the effectiveness of the adsorption-desorption process and the separation of the photogenerated electron-hole pair are also substantially affected^{16,18,20,21,25,30}. In the present study, an increase in pH from 3 to 7, the value of rate constant has been doubled (Table 5). At pH 7, the maximum initial rate is achieved and with further increase in pH, the rate

Table 5. Effect of pH

$[SO^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[ZnO] = 200 \text{ mg}$,
light intensity = 17500 lux and Temp. = $30 \pm 0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

pH	<i>k</i> (min^{-1})	<i>t</i> _{1/2} (min)
3.21	0.012	57.75
4.32	0.024	28.87
5.23	0.031	22.35
6.12	0.040	17.32
7.33	0.036	19.25
8.21	0.021	33.00
9.22	0.011	63.00

of photodegradation decreased. The low initial reaction rates at acidic or at alkali pH values are due to dissolution and photo dissolution of ZnO^{31} . The semiconductor ZnO is amphoteric in nature. At acidic pH, ZnO can react

with acids to produce the corresponding salt, while at alkaline pH, it can react with a base to form complexes like $[Zn(OH)_4]^{2-}$. The pH of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ aqueous dye solution was 6.10. At this pH, *k* value was found to be 0.040 min^{-1} and corresponding *t*_{1/2} value was 29 min for an irradiation period of 1 h. Hence, *k* value increases with increasing pH values.

Effect of persulphate ion :

The effect of persulphate ion (electron scavenger)^{32,33,5,25}, on the photocatalytic degradation was investigated by varying its concentration from 1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 6). Rate constant values increases with increasing amount of persulphate ion and attained maxi-

Table 6. Effect of potassium persulphate

$[SO^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[ZnO] = 200 \text{ mg}$,
light intensity = 17500 lux, pH = 6.12 and
Temp. = $30 \pm 0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

$K_2S_2O_8$ (mol dm^{-3})	<i>k</i> (min^{-1})	<i>t</i> _{1/2} (min)
0	0.040	17.32
1.0×10^{-6}	0.057	12.15
3.0×10^{-6}	0.067	10.34
5.0×10^{-6}	0.076	9.11
7.0×10^{-6}	0.094	7.37
9.0×10^{-6}	0.108	6.41
1.0×10^{-5}	0.124	5.56

mum value for $7.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The increase in *K* values may be due to the formation of $SO_4^{\bullet-}$ as

where e^-_{CB} is the electron generated in the ZnO conduction band and DOC_1 symbolises the organics partially transformed prior to the complete oxidation until carbon dioxide. Obviously the reactions in (1) and (2) accelerate the photocatalytic reaction rate by avoiding e^-/h^+ recombination.

The sulphate radical anion ($SO_4^{\bullet-}$) thus formed is a very strong oxidant ($E^0 = 2.6 \text{ eV}$) and may act in following three possible ways with organic compounds : (i) by

abstracting a hydrogen atom from saturated carbon, (ii) by adding to unsaturated or aromatic carbon and (iii) by removing one electron from the carboxylate anions and from certain neutral molecules^{34,35}. It traps the photogenerated electron and/or generates hydroxyl radicals reducing the possibility of electron-hole recombination³⁶. The hydroxyl radical and sulphate radical anion being powerful oxidants degrade the dye molecule at a faster rate. The $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ has the unique nature of attacking the dye molecule at various positions and hence the fragmentation of the dye molecules is rapid. Further increase in persulphate concentration has decreased the degradation rate owing to the adsorption of excess sulphate ions formed during the reaction on the surface of ZnO deactivating a section of the catalyst²². It must be noted that the activity of the oxidants is not only due to the entrapment of the photogenerated electrons but, also due to their ability to absorb light and act as sensitizer through the production of hydroxyl and sulphate radicals.

Effect of sodium carbonate :

For the fixing of dye on the fabrics and fastness of the colour sodium carbonate is often used. Consequently, the wastewater from the dyeing operation contains substantial amount of carbonate ions. Hence, it is important to study the effect of carbonate ions in the photodegradation efficiency. Experiments were performed with sodium carbonate in the range 1.0×10^{-5} to 9.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} . It is observed that k value gradually decreased with increasing amount of carbonate ion (Table 7). The decrease in the rate of degradation in the presence of carbonate ion is due to the hydroxyl scavenging property of carbonate

Table 7. Effect of sodium carbonate

$[\text{SO}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{ZnO}] = 200$ mg,
light intensity = 17500 lux, pH = 6.12 and
Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

Na_2CO_3 (mol dm^{-3})	k (min^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
0	0.040	17.32
1.0×10^{-5}	0.036	19.25
3.0×10^{-5}	0.034	20.38
5.0×10^{-5}	0.032	21.65
7.0×10^{-5}	0.032	21.65
9.0×10^{-5}	0.026	26.65

ions^{26,37} as shown in following reactions :

Hence, the presence of auxiliary chemicals in the dye solution like sodium carbonate hinders the photocatalytic degradation of dyes.

Effect of sodium chloride :

The photocatalytic degradation efficiency was considerably decreased upon the addition of sodium chloride that is usually in the textile industry waste water in high concentrations. The photodegradation studies were carried out with sodium chloride in the range 3.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} keeping dye solution concentration of 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm^{-3} . The k' value of the degradation process decreases gradually with increase in the amount of chloride ions (Table 8). The retarding effect of NaCl on degradation rate can be explained as a result of the

Table 8. Effect of sodium chloride

$[\text{SO}^+] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{ZnO}] = 200$ mg,
light intensity = 17500 lux, pH = 6.12 and
Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

NaCl (mol dm^{-3})	k (min^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
0	0.040	17.32
3.0×10^{-6}	0.034	20.38
5.0×10^{-6}	0.031	22.35
7.0×10^{-6}	0.030	23.10
9.0×10^{-6}	0.025	27.72
1.0×10^{-5}	0.020	34.56

reaction of photogenerated holes and hydroxyl radicals with chloride ions to form chloride radicals.

The Cl^\bullet and $\text{Cl}_2^{\cdot-}$ radicals are in principle and capable oxidizing pollutants, but react with lower rate than with OH radical, due to their lower oxidation potentials³⁸. The generation of Cl^\bullet radicals leads also to the formation of chlorinated organic compound³⁹ which are known as very harmful substances and therefore longer treatment periods are needed.

Effect of the light intensity :

The influence of light intensity on the rate of degrada-

tion has been examined at constant dye concentration (2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³) and catalyst loading (200 mg/50 mL). It is evident that the rate of decolourisation and photodegradation increases with increasing light intensity (Table 9), because the visible radiation generates the photons required for the electron transfer from the valence band to the conduction band of a semiconductor photo-

Table 9. Effect of light intensity

[SO⁺] = 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [ZnO] = 200 mg, pH = 6.12 and Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

Light intensity $\times 10^3$ (lux)	k (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
10	0.028	24.75
15	0.036	19.25
18	0.040	17.32
20	0.053	13.01
25	0.071	9.70
30	0.108	6.41

catalyst and the energy of a photon is related to its wavelength and the overall energy input to a photocatalytic process is independent on light intensity. The rate of degradation increases with increased radiation on the catalyst surface resulting in more hydroxyl radicals^{40,41}.

Efficiency of other photocatalysts :

Experiments were performed with other photocatalysts as well (Table 10). Generally, semiconductors having large band gaps are good photocatalysts. It has already been

Table 10. Effect of other photocatalysts

[SO⁺] = 2.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, amount of photocatalyst = 200 mg, light intensity = 17500 lux, pH = 6.12 and Temp. = 30 ± 0.3 °C

Photocatalyst	k (min ⁻¹)	Band gap (eV)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
ZnO	0.040	3.2	17.32
TiO ₂	0.021	3.1	33.00
CdS	0.019	2.3	36.47

reported that semiconductors such as ZnO and TiO₂ have band gaps larger than 3 eV show strong photocatalytic activity. The conduction and valence band potentials of both ZnO and TiO₂ are larger than the corresponding redox potentials of H⁺/H₂ and H₂O/O₂ and the photogenerated electron and hole can be separated efficiently. CdS with smaller band gaps show less activity

since its conduction band is much lower than that of ZnO and TiO₂. The electron (CB) in these semiconductors rapidly falls into the hole thus showing reduced activity⁴². Under given conditions, ZnO has been found to be the most efficient photocatalyst of these three.

Effect of nitrogen :

The effect of bubbling of nitrogen through the aqueous suspension of the dye on the reaction rate constants has been studied. It is observed that photodegradation is severely retarded by purging with pure nitrogen as it expels the dissolved oxygen. The dissolved oxygen in the solution plays an important role by trapping the conduction band electrons forming superoxide ions (O₂^{•-}) and thus preventing the electron-hole recombination.

and at same time H₂O₂ is formed from O₂^{•-}.

Mechanism :

It is a well established fact that by the irradiation on an aqueous ZnO suspension with light energy greater than the band gap energy of the semiconductor ($h\nu > E_g = 3.2$ eV) conduction band electrons (e^-) and valence band holes ($h\nu_B$) are generated. A fraction of the photogenerated carriers recombine in the bulk of the semiconductor, while the rest reach the surface, where the holes, as well as the electrons act as powerful oxidants, respectively. The photogenerated electrons react with the adsorbed molecular O₂ on the ZnO particle sites, reducing it to a superoxide radical anion O₂^{•-}, while the photogenerated holes can oxidize either the dye molecule directly or the OH⁻ ions and the H₂O molecules adsorbed the ZnO surface to •OR radicals. The •OH radicals formed on the illuminated semiconductor surface are quite strong oxidizing agents with a standard electrode potential of 3.2 eV. These can easily attack the adsorbed organic molecule or those located close to the surface of the catalyst, thus leading finally to their complete mineralization. In photocatalytic oxidation process, the generation of hydroxyl radicals takes places in two possible ways. Semiconductor ZnO, upon absorption of a photon of suitable energy can act as a photocatalytic substrate by producing electron-hole pair by the excitement of electrons from valence band to conduction band. The photogenerated holes that are able to migrate to the hydroxylated surface can create the highly reactive and short-lived hydroxyl radical •OH^{5,11,43-45}.

In second way, the dye molecules act as a sensitizer by the absorption of visible light, and the transfer of photogenerated electrons from the dye molecule to semiconductor has been reported to be very effective. The various steps of overall mechanism envisioned are :

The eq. (26) depicts the absorption of light by the dye molecule (Dye*). This excited dye (Dye*) injects an electron to the conduction band of ZnO in eq. (28), where it is scavenged by O₂ to form active oxygen molecule as shown in eq. (29). Further active oxygen molecule formed in eq. (29) subsequently reacts with H₂O to generate OH[•] radicals. These active radicals drive the photodegradation or mineralization of the dye molecule.

Photodegradation products :

The complete decomposition to CO₂ via photocatalytic reactions is of great significance in water treatment, because it is unequivocal evidence of total destruction of organic compounds in water. In the order to study the extent of mineralization of over illuminated ZnO suspension COD measurements were carried out. The decrease in the value of COD (Table 1) is an indication of degradation process. The evolution of CO₂ during the degradation is the evidence of total destruction of dye in the aqueous medium. The decrease in pH and increase in conductivity are indicative the formation of some mineral acid and ions in the system respectively. The destruction of the dye has been confirmed by the COD method.

Conclusions :

In the present work the photocatalytic degradation of Safranin-O, has been studied under artificial visible light

illumination. It is observed that ZnO is an efficient catalyst, both in respect of decolourisation as well as mineralization. From the results reported above it is clear that under the specific experimental conditions the synergetic action of ZnO with oxidants such as H₂O₂ and K₂S₂O₈ leads to a substantial increase of the initial reaction rate and the extent of mineralization in comparison to using ZnO alone. The photodegradation of Safranin-O followed first order kinetics according to Langmuir-Hinshelwood model. The illumination time, loading of the catalyst and pH significantly influences the reaction rate. The presence of inorganic salts and sodium carbonate hinder the photocatalytic degradation. The complete mineralization of the dye is possible in a short irradiation period, if the concentration of the dye, catalyst loading, pH, amount of H₂O₂ and persulphate are optimised.

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